

THE IMPORTANCE OF COMMUNICATION IN STUDENTS' EDUCATIONAL ACTIVITY

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Abstract. *This article highlights the importance of communication in the educational activities of students.*

Key words: *communication, communication, verbal and non-verbal communication, personality, speech.*

ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ОБЩЕНИЯ В ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ СТУДЕНТОВ

Аннотация. *В данной статье подчеркивается значение общения в учебной деятельности студентов.*

Ключевые слова: *общение, общение, вербальное и невербальное общение, личность, речь.*

Communication is a process unique to humans. People have a need to communicate with each other during their activities. Mutual communication is, of course, the most basic element of human society. In the dictionary of psychology, the concept of communication is given two different definitions:

1. Communication is the process of communication and its development required by the need for cooperative activity;
2. Communication is the interaction of subjects through the sign system.

Communication is a multifaceted process of the development of bonds between people arising from the needs of joint activity.

Communication (relationship) involves the exchange of information between the participants. This takes into account the communicative aspect of the relationship. The concept of dialogue should be distinguished from communication.

Communication refers to the exchange of information between living and non-living systems. The exchange of signals between animals, human communication with technical means - this is all communication. Communication can only be done between people. It is in the process of communicating and interacting with others that a human child becomes a person, acquires social experience and culture.

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(path of individual development). During the activity, new relationships and connections are formed between people.

Another aspect of communication is the mutual action of the participants in the relationship - communicating not only with words, but also with actions. The next aspect of the relationship is the ability of the interlocutors to perceive each other. For example, we treat a person with respect or contempt before starting a conversation. So, in the process of communication, communicative (information transfer), interactive (mutual action) and perceptive (mutual) perception is carried out. In fact, the social experience of each person, his human image, qualities, and even defects are the product of communication processes.

A person separated from society, deprived of the opportunity to communicate, can retain individual qualities, but he cannot be a person. Therefore, we analyze its functions in order to imagine the importance of communication in the development of a person.

The most elementary function of any communication is to ensure that the interlocutors understand each other. It starts with welcoming us to our people with a sincere greeting and an open face. One of the rarest and greatest qualities of the Uzbek people is that when someone comes into their house, they welcome them with an open face, they see them, they ask about how they are doing. It is characteristic that we feel such sincere reception even when we go to condolence. Other nations and peoples also have such primary contact methods, that is, this aspect has a national identity. Its second important function is the foundation of social experience. A human child is socialized only in the circle of people, forms the necessary human characteristics.

The fact that a human child was abducted by monsters, and then reappeared among humans after a certain period of time showed that "Mowglis" continue to develop as biological beings, but lag behind in socialization. In addition, it has been proven in many psychological experiments that such a condition limits the child's cognitive abilities.

Another important function of communication is that it prepares and inspires a person for this or that activity. A person who is distant from the group of people, who is out of their sight, does not even go to work, and even if he does, he can do work that benefits only himself and not society. For example, many studies have studied the effect of isolation, i.e. leaving a person alone, on the human psyche. For example, we treat a person with respect or contempt before entering into a relationship. So, in the process of communication, communicative (information transfer), interactive (mutual action) and perceptive (mutual) perception is carried out. Each person's "I" is formed in the process of communication with others. A person's life path develops first in the family, kindergarten, school, institute, workplace, among the elderly, that is, in groups and communities. If our need for communication is not met, our mind will not develop. We get satisfaction from communication with someone, and in some cases we feel unsatisfied. Pedagogical communication is one of the types of communication and occupies an important place in pedagogical activity.

Communication takes a leading place among the activities performed by people, it satisfies the most important human need - the need to live in society and consider oneself as an individual. That is why it is important for everyone. Scientists have also learned that it does not lead to harm. However, any loneliness and lack of communication can lead to imbalance, emotionality, stuttering, anxiety,

causes feelings of self-doubt, sadness, and anxiety. It is interesting to note that those who were not condemned to loneliness began to speak after a certain time. At first, it is about what one sees or feels, but later there is a need to talk about something. For example, a scientist named M. Sifr lived in a cave for 63 days to realize his scientific goals. He later wrote that a few days later, he caught a spider on the ground and had a dialogue with it starts. "We," he wrote, "were lonely living beings in this lifeless cave. I began to talk to the spider, I began to worry about his fate..."

Full satisfaction of a person's non-communicative needs also affects his work performance. People, their presence, the fact that there is an opportunity to talk to each other in this environment often increases a person's ability to work, especially in the work that is done while talking, and in the operations that are performed side by side, people are more dependent on the colleague in front of them. , will find strength and additional will to work faster. True, in this cooperation, if he likes the person next to him, if there is a feeling of mutual sympathy between them, then the person comes to work "as if he came to a holiday".

That is why the American sociologist and psychologist John Moreno studied the direct effect of this factor on productivity at the beginning of last year and used sociometric technology, that is, on the basis of a questionnaire, he identified those who liked each other and those who rejected each other, and introduced the methodology of sociometry was founded.

Humanity's tool of communication is language, and people carry out all their relationships and communications with each other using speech. Our wise people have a lot of instructive sayings about the rules of speaking, being careful with the language, thinking about every word, every sentence, in short - speaking etiquette and culture of communication. According to one of them, the honor and pride of a person can be seen in his cultural speech. Someone who does not follow the manners of speech does not show humanity. It is appropriate and meaningful if it is not spoken, it is useful to listen to it in silence. In this regard, we found it necessary to cite eight rules of speech: Everyone should refrain from words that harm others. For this, it is necessary to be careful with the language, not to say words that hurt people's tongues, hurt people's hearts, touch their sense of honor, trample on their honor and dignity.

It is necessary to be kind all the time, to always speak well and meaningfully, because the hurt from the tongue is worse than the hurt from the spear. Thus, communication is the internal psychological mechanism of people's cooperative activities in society. Moreover, given the need to make various production decisions not individually, but collegially, in the current conditions of new democratic relations, the culture of people's behavior and communication techniques are important factors of labor productivity and efficiency.

REFERENCES

1. Абдуллажонова М., Исоқова М., Зокирова М., Исроилжонов С. Ижтимоий психологик тренингдан практикум. Ўқув-услубий нашр, Фарғона. «Фарғона» нашриёти. 2003.- 68 б.
2. Алешина Е.А. Когнитивные нарушения, тревога и депрессия у беременных: современный взгляд на проблему. Обзор литературы // Перинатология. - 2016. - Т. 135, № 02. - С. 22-27.

3. Алфимова М.В., Лапин И.А., Аксенова Е.В., Мельникова Т.С. Влияние тревоги на когнитивные процессы депрессивном синдроме // Социальная и клиническая психиатрия. - 2017. - Т.27, №1. - С. 5-12.
4. Ананьев Б.Г. О проблемах современного человекознания. – СПб.: Питер. 2001. – 272 с.
5. Akramova. F, R.Abdullayeva. Oilaviy hayotni o'rganishga oid psixologik testlar.T. 2002. Respublika «Oila» markazi.